

The Influence of Competence and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance with Self-Efficacy as an Intervening Variable A Study at the Human Resources and Health Division of PT Kereta Api Indonesia (Persero) DAOP 6 Yogyakarta

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to analyze the influence of competence and organizational culture on employee performance, with self-efficacy as an intervening variable among employees of the Human Resources and Health Division at PT Kereta Api Indonesia (Persero) DAOP 6 Yogyakarta. A quantitative approach was employed, using a census sampling method involving 60 employees as respondents. Data were collected through a questionnaire and analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with the Partial Least Square (PLS) method via SmartPLS 4.0. The results show that both competence and organizational culture have a direct positive influence on employee performance. Furthermore, self-efficacy plays a significant mediating role in the relationship between competence and employee performance, as well as between organizational culture and employee performance. These findings highlight the importance of enhancing employee self-efficacy, especially in critical divisions, to maximize their contribution to organizational goals. This research contributes theoretically by addressing the research gap on the mediating role of self-efficacy, and practically by providing insights for HR development strategies in state-owned enterprises.

KEYWORDS: Competence, Employee Performance, Organizational Culture, Self-Efficacy.

INTRODUCTION

The success of an organization in achieving its goals is strongly influenced by the effective management of human resources. Employees are vital assets, directly contributing to operational success and organizational sustainability (Armstrong, 2006). Hence, enhancing employee performance is crucial to maintaining competitive advantage and achieving long-term growth. Performance refers to how effectively and efficiently individuals fulfill their responsibilities, impacting the realization of organizational objectives (Robbins & Judge, 2017).

Competence is one of the key factors affecting employee performance. It is defined as a combination of knowledge, skills, and attitudes required to perform tasks effectively (Spencer & Spencer, 1993). Competent employees are generally more adaptive, capable of working independently, and able to make appropriate decisions in dynamic work environments (Mangkunegara, 2015; Dessler, 2020).

Another important factor is organizational culture, which consists of shared values, norms, and assumptions that guide behavior and shape organizational identity (Schein, 2010). A strong and well-integrated culture supports collaboration, increases engagement, and aligns individual behavior with organizational goals (Robbins & Judge, 2019).

In addition, psychological factors such as self-efficacy defined as an individual's belief in their capability to accomplish tasks play a mediating role in enhancing employee outcomes (Bandura, 1997). Employees with high self-efficacy tend to be more motivated, resilient, and persistent in overcoming challenges, leading to better performance (Santrock, 2011). Self-efficacy is also influenced by competence and organizational culture, making it an essential intervening variable in performance models (Mulyanto et al., 2023).

At PT Kereta Api Indonesia (Persero) DAOP 6 Yogyakarta, particularly within the Human Resources and Health Division, internal performance evaluations in 2024 revealed performance issues, including low KPI scores, suboptimal training application, and weak collaboration. Pre survey results further indicated that many employees lacked confidence in handling challenges and preferred working individually despite tasks requiring teamwork.

Although many studies have explored the relationship between competence, organizational culture, and employee performance, the findings remain inconsistent. Some research has found significant positive relationships (Mulyanto et al., 2023), while others

reported non-significant or even negative effects (Yulianty et al., 2021; Aprilian et al., 2024; Nurcahaya et al., 2023). Moreover, the mediating role of self efficacy in these relationships has not been thoroughly examined, particularly within Indonesia’s state-owned enterprises in the transportation sector.

Thus, this study seeks to address these inconsistencies by investigating the direct and indirect influence of competence and organizational culture on employee performance, with self-efficacy as a mediating variable. The findings are expected to contribute to the development of theory in human resource management and offer practical insights for performance improvement strategies at PT Kereta Api Indonesia (Persero) DAOP 6 Yogyakarta.

LITERATURE REVIEW

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Employee Performance

Employee performance is defined as the outcome of an individual’s work measured against predetermined standards (Robbins & Judge, 2017). According to Simamora (2016), performance indicators include work results, job knowledge, initiative, mental dexterity, attitude, and punctuality.

Competence

Competence refers to the underlying characteristics of an individual that lead to superior performance in a job (Spencer & Spencer, 1993). Indicators include motives, traits, self-concept, knowledge, and skills (Moeheriono, 2012).

Organizational Culture

Organizational culture is a system of shared values and norms that influence behavior within an organization (Schein, 2010). Indicators include innovation and risk-taking, attention to detail, outcome orientation, people orientation, team orientation, aggressiveness, and stability (Robbins & Judge, 2019).

Organizational Culture

Self-efficacy is the belief in one’s capabilities to execute tasks and attain goals (Bandura, 1997). Dimensions include magnitude, strength, and generality (Santrock, 2011).

FRANMEWORK

Hypothesis

- H1 : Competence has a positive effect on employee performance at PT Kereta Api Indonesia (Persero) DAOP 6 Yogyakarta.
H2 : Organizational culture has a positive effect on employee performance at PT Kereta Api Indonesia (Persero) DAOP 6 Yogyakarta.
H3 : Competence has a positive effect on employee performance with self-efficacy as an intervening variable at PT Kereta Api Indonesia (Persero) DAOP 6 Yogyakarta.
H4 : Organizational culture has a positive effect on employee performance with self-efficacy as an intervening variable at PT Kereta Api Indonesia (Persero) DAOP 6 Yogyakarta.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study utilized a quantitative approach with a descriptive and associative research design. The population comprised all employees of the Human Resources and Health Division at PT Kereta Api Indonesia (Persero) DAOP 6 Yogyakarta, totaling 60 individuals. A census sampling technique was employed. Data were collected through structured questionnaires measured using a Likert scale. The instrument was tested for validity and reliability, with analysis conducted using SmartPLS 4.0 software. Measurement and structural models were assessed using convergent validity, discriminant validity, composite reliability, R², and hypothesis testing through bootstrapping.

RESULT AND DISSCUSION

Mean Results of Each Variable

No.	Variabels	Mean
1.	Competence	3.41
2.	Organizational culture	3.36
3.	Self Efficacy	4.42
4.	Employee performance	4.34

Based on the descriptive analysis results, the average scores of each research variable are as follows: competence (3.41), organizational culture (3.36), self-efficacy (4.42), and employee performance (4.34). Table 1 shows that the competence variable received a mean score of 3.41, indicating that employees rated their competencies as fairly good. This suggests that, overall, the employees perceive themselves to have adequate capabilities to perform their responsibilities effectively. The organizational culture variable obtained a mean of 3.36, which implies that employees considered the organizational culture to be moderately strong. While several cultural values are upheld, there may still be opportunities to enhance alignment and cohesion within the organization. The self-efficacy variable recorded the highest mean at 4.42, which demonstrates that most employees feel confident in their ability to complete tasks and handle challenges. This result indicates a high level of self-belief and psychological readiness among staff members. Meanwhile, the employee performance variable yielded a mean of 4.34, reflecting a strong self-assessment of task completion, responsibility, and effectiveness. It suggests that employees believe their performance contributes positively to achieving organizational goals.

Validity Test

Variabel	Indikator	Outer	Description
Competence	X1.1_1	0.776	Valid
	X1.1_2	0.824	Valid
	X1.2_1	0.844	Valid
	X1.2_2	0.762	Valid
	X1.3_1	0.868	Valid

	X1.3_2	0.866	Valid
	X1.4_1	0.764	Valid
	X1.4_2	0.910	Valid
	X1.5_1	0.880	Valid
	X1.5_2	0.771	Valid
Organizational culture	X2.1_1	0.897	Valid
	X2.1_2	0.811	Valid
	X2.2_1	0.824	Valid
	X2.3_1	0.832	Valid
	X2.3_2	0.756	Valid
	X2.4_1	0.79	Valid
	X2.4_2	0.793	Valid
	X2.5_1	0.803	Valid
	X2.5_2	0.779	Valid
	X2.6_1	0.707	Valid
	X2.6_2	0.847	Valid
	X2.7_1	0.798	Valid
	X2.7_2	0.775	Valid
	Employee performance	Y1.1_1	0.774
Y1.1_2		0.734	Valid
Y1.1_3		0.805	Valid
Y1.2_1		0.774	Valid
Y1.2_2		0.799	Valid
Y1.3_1		0.887	Valid
Y1.3_2		0.859	Valid

	Y1.4_1	0.775	Valid
	Y1.4_2	0.840	Valid
	Y1.5_1	0.851	Valid
	Y1.5_2	0.715	Valid
	Y1.5_3	0.828	Valid
	Y1.6_1	0.745	Valid
	Y1.6_2	0.805	Valid
Self Efficacy	Z1.1_1	0.860	Valid
	Z1.1_2	0.750	Valid
	Z1.2_1	0.801	Valid
	Z1.2_2	0.857	Valid
	Z1.3_1	0.800	Valid
	Z1.3_2	0.895	Valid
	Z1.3_3	0.796	Valid
	Z1.4_1	0.858	Valid
	Z1.4_2	0.825	Valid
	Z1.4_3	0.687	Valid
	Z1.5_1	0.765	Valid
	Z1.5_2	0.858	Valid

Source : Primary data processed (2025)

The results presented in the table indicate that all outer loading values exceed the minimum threshold of 0.50, confirming that all indicators effectively represent their respective constructs. Thus, convergent validity has been established for all five research variables.

Validity Test

One method to assess construct validity is through discriminant validity. Discriminant validity ensures that a construct is truly distinct from other constructs by confirming that the construct measures what it is intended to measure and not something else. According to Ghazali and Latan (2020), a good Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value should be above 0.50, both for confirmatory and exploratory research. Based on the results of testing on 60 respondents, the AVE values for each variable were obtained as shown in the following table:

Variabel	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Kriteria	Keterangan
Kompetensi	0.686	>0.5	Valid
Budaya organisasional	0.643	>0.5	Valid
Kinerja Karyawan	0.641	>0.5	Valid
Self Efficacy	0.664	>0.5	Valid

Source : Primary data processed (2025)

Composite Reliability

One measure of construct reliability is composite reliability, which evaluates the internal consistency of indicators within a construct. To assess this, two common statistical tools are used: composite reliability (CR) and Cronbach’s alpha. Both metrics aim to determine the extent to which the indicators consistently measure the same latent variable. An instrument is considered reliable if both values exceed 0.70.

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	Keterangan	Composite Reliability	Keterangan
Kompetensi	0.949	Reliabel	0.956	Reliabel
Budaya organisasional	0.954	Reliabel	0.959	Reliabel
Kinerja Karyawan	0.957	Reliabel	0.961	Reliabel
Self Efficacy	0.953	Reliabel	0.959	Reliabel

Source: Primary data processed (2025)

Based on Table 4, all variables in this study have a composite reliability value greater than 0.7, indicating that all variables have met the established standards and the next process can proceed. Based on Table 4, it can also be seen that all question items show a good level of reliability, as the Cronbach's Alpha value for each variable is greater than 0.7, thus the questionnaire instrument in this study can be declared reliable.

Hypothesis

In this study, hypothesis testing was conducted using the bootstrapping method in the SmartPLS application, by comparing the t-statistic value with the t-table at a significance level of p-value 0.05. If the t-statistic is greater than 1.96, it can be concluded that the exogenous variable has a significant effect on the endogenous variable. The criteria for hypothesis acceptance are met when the p-value ≤ 0.05 , and the hypothesis is accepted if the t-statistic \geq t-table (Ghozali & Latan, 2020). According to Ghozali and Latan (2020), when a model involves an intervening or mediating variable, multiple regression is not an appropriate analytical method. As an alternative, Path Analysis is considered more suitable. In this study, Path Analysis is employed to examine both the direct and indirect relationships among the variables in the model.

Hypothesis Testing through Path Coefficient Results

Hubungan	Original sample	Sample mean	Standard deviation	T statistics	P values	Keterangan
H1 : X1->Y	0.283	0.291	0.086	3.275	0.001	Signifikan
H2 : X2->Y	0.267	0.273	0.089	2.988	0.003	Signifikan

Source: Primary data processed (2025)

Hypothesis Testing through Specific Indirect Effects

Hubungan	Original sample	Sample mean	Standard deviation	T statistics	P values	Keterangan
H3 : X2 -> Z -> Y	0.327	0.320	0.080	4.081	0.000	Signifikan
H4 : X1 -> Z -> Y	0.334	0.327	0.075	4.457	0.000	Signifikan

Source: Primary data processed (2025)

Based on the hypothesis testing results presented in Tables 5 and 6, several conclusions can be drawn. The first hypothesis (H1) is supported, indicating that competence has a positive and significant effect on employee performance in the HR and Health Division of PT Kereta Api Indonesia (Persero) Daop 6 Yogyakarta, with a p-value of 0.001, a t-statistic of 3.275, and an original sample value of 0.283. The second hypothesis (H2) is also accepted, showing that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee performance, as evidenced by a p-value of 0.003, a t-statistic of 2.988, and an original sample value of 0.267. Furthermore, the third hypothesis (H3) confirms that competence has a positive and significant indirect effect on employee performance through self efficacy, with a p-value of 0.000, a t-statistic of 4.081, and an original sample value of 0.327. Lastly, the fourth hypothesis (H4) is supported, demonstrating that organizational culture has a positive and significant indirect effect on employee performance through self efficacy, with a p-value of 0.000, a t-statistic of 4.457, and an original sample value of 0.334. These findings highlight both the direct and mediating effects within the proposed model.

CONSLUSION

This study investigated the influence of competence and organizational culture on employee performance, with self-efficacy as a mediating variable, using data from 60 employees in the Human Resources and Health Division at PT Kereta Api Indonesia (Persero) Daerah Operasi 6 Yogyakarta. The results revealed that both competence and organizational culture have a positive and significant impact on employee performance. Competent employees those who possess the necessary knowledge, skills, and attitudes tend to perform their duties more effectively. Similarly, a strong and supportive organizational culture enhances motivation and fosters an environment conducive to high performance. Furthermore, both competence and organizational culture were found to significantly influence self-efficacy, meaning that employees who are well-equipped and who operate in a positive cultural environment are more confident in their abilities to accomplish work tasks. Finally, self-efficacy was shown to significantly mediate the relationship between competence and organizational culture on performance, indicating that employees' belief in their own capabilities strengthens the impact of these two factors. Overall, the findings highlight the importance of fostering both competence and a supportive organizational culture to boost self-efficacy and improve employee performance.

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